

FORMS OF STUDENTS' ACADEMIC MOBILITY ORGANIZATION IN RUSSIAN UNIVERSITIES

ORGANIZACIÓN DE FORMAS DE MOVILIDAD ACADÉMICA DE ESTUDIANTES EN UNIVERSIDADES RUSAS

Alina Shakirova¹, Landysh Gizyatova²

Alina A. Shakirova

Landysh A. Gizyatova

RESUMEN

El objetivo de esta investigación fue sistematizar diversas formas de organización de la movilidad académica de los estudiantes en las universidades rusas. Estudiamos los trabajos científicos sobre el problema y presentamos las principales formas de organización de la movilidad académica de los estudiantes en tres niveles: internacional, regional e institucional. Analizamos la experiencia de las principales universidades rusas en la organización de la movilidad académica de los estudiantes y nuestro descubrimiento muestra que la movilidad académica es una de las actividades anteriores de la cooperación internacional de las universidades.

Palabras clave: educación, estudiantes, movilidad académica, Rusia, Organización de formas de movilidad.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this research was to systematize various forms of students' academic mobility organization in Russian universities. We studied the scientific works on the problem and presented the main forms of students' academic mobility organization at three levels: international, regional and institutional. We analyzed the experience of the leading Russian universities in organizing students' academic mobility and our finding shows Academic mobility is one of the prior activities of the university's international cooperation.

Keywords: education, students, academic mobility, Russia, forms of mobility Organization.

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¹ Senior lecturer, without degree Kazan Federal University / Institute of International Relations, History and Oriental Studies, E-mail: AlinaAShakirova@kpfu.ru, vk: <https://vk.com/id795655>

² Senior lecturer, without degree Kazan Federal University/ Institute of International Relations, History and Oriental Studies , E-mail: lgizyato@kpfu.ru, www.orcid.org: <https://orcid.org/my-orcid>

INTRODUCTION

In Russia millions of students take part in the mobility programs and the analysis of academic mobility is very topical. Most of the scholars analyze academic mobility in terms of the Bologna process and consider it as a means of internationalization process in the sphere of higher education (Shakirova, 2016). Academic mobility is the means that helps universities to attract more students, thus becoming the main indicator of a university to be included in the Top-university rankings (Ziyatdinova, Bezrukov, Sanger and Osipov, 2016).

There are a wide number of the forms of students' academic mobility today. However there is no universal classification of these forms. Some researchers devoted their works to this problem. Most of the existing research papers consider forms of academic mobility in the context of international collaboration between higher education establishments. Modern universities take an active part in the process of the worldwide integration which involves many countries. The main aim of universities is mutual profitable cooperation which leads to the cultural, educational and professional exchange and moreover – financial aid to the universities' budget. With the development of international collaboration the number of different forms of this collaboration increases rapidly. Academic mobility may be taken not only as the example of international collaboration because there are some programs stimulating mobility inside of the country.

The main objective of this article titled “Forms of Students Academic Mobility Organization in Russian Universities” is to systematize various forms of students' academic mobility organization in Russian universities.

METHODOLOGY

We used the following theoretical methods: analysis and synthesis, theoretical analysis of the scientific literature on the problem of academic mobility and its forms. The theoretical basis of the research is the conceptual ideas of the scientific researches in the systematization of academic mobility and its organization on the international, regional and institutional levels. Systematic approach allowed us to research various approaches to the identification of different forms of academic mobility and to analyze their common and different features.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We distinguish the main three levels of the students' academic mobility forms. The first level is the *international* level, presented by international and European mobility programs initiated by European Union. The most significant is the Erasmus program. Launched in 1987 this program provided more than 1 million students, teachers and administrators of higher education institutions to gain experience of living and analyzing abroad by 2020. By 2008-2009 this figure increased by another 1 million and by 2013 reached 3 million participants (A Statistical Overview

of the Erasmus Program in 2012-13, 2015).

For the period 2014-2020 the Erasmus + program budget is about 15 billion Euros, which is 40% higher than in the previous period. It is planned to provide more than 4 million people with grants and subsidies for training, research and internships (Action Plan for International Cooperation, 2014).

In 2014 a new large-scale program of the European Union, ERASMUS + which will operate till 2020, was launched. This program has several areas: education, training, youth and sports. It will replace a number of previous programs, such as ERASMUS MUNDUS, TEMPUS, LEONARDO DA VINCI and other. ERASMUS + provides grants for students, teachers and trainers to stay in a foreign institution and develop their skills and abilities. The program also supports organizations that are transnational partners and promotes the exchange of innovative methods of work in the field of education and training.

The second level is the *regional* level of academic mobility organization. The International department of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation realizes the Program of outgoing international academic mobility. The main aim of the program is providing opportunities for citizens of the Russian Federation to receive educational services (short-term internships) in foreign countries that are fully or partially paid for by the host country, as well as gaining experience in teaching and research in foreign countries. Those who wish to participate in the program can choose one of the proposed countries, analyze the requirements and apply for open competitions for the following hosting parties: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Italy, China, Romania, Singapore and others. In 2016 528 students, graduates and teachers were sent to 21 foreign universities for short-term studies (Caulfield, Chang, Dollard & Elshaug, 2004).

One of the Russian projects contributing to the development of academic mobility is also the Mikhail Prokhorov Fund. It is the Charity Fund for Cultural Initiatives, which was established in 2004 on the initiative of a Russian businessman Mikhail Prokhorov and became the first charitable organization in Russia with a regional strategy of work. One of the fund's projects is the project "Academic Mobility". In 2016 the total grant fund was 195,650.00 United States Dollars.

The fund finances grants for participation in scientific conferences and seminars, work in archives and libraries, internships in scientific institutions of the country and abroad for graduates, postgraduates and young teachers under 35 years for no more than 2 weeks. However, not all regions can participate in this program. According to the annual report on the Fund's work in 2015 310 applications out of 1130 submitted were supported (Global Education, 2017).

The Government of the Russian Federation implements the State Program "Global Education", which involves funding up to 41,538.00 United States Dollars a year to finance education (for master degree, graduate or postgraduate education), residence and various expenses. In December 2015 more than 700 applications were submitted, 153 of which were approved as winners. The goal of the program is to train at least 718 citizens of the Russian Federation in the leading foreign educational organizations in the areas of priority for the Russian economy (Global Education, 2017).

"Algarysh" is a program of grants from the Government of the Republic of Tatarstan for the training and retraining of citizens in Russian and foreign educational and scientific organizations. This is the first regional program of this kind in Russia.

Currently, the program provides funding for the following categories of grantees from Tatarstan:

- Young specialists, graduate students and young scientists under 35;
- Teachers and researchers of universities of the Republic of Tatarstan;
- Employees of general educational institutions and institutions of primary and secondary vocational education;
- Double diplomas;
- Educational organizations of higher professional education;
- Project teams.

Particular attention in the program is given to support the talented youth. More than 70% of the total program budget is invested annually for the preparation and internship of specialists, graduate students and young scientists up to 35. The grant covers the costs of training, accommodation, meals, educational literature, pocket expenses and travel tickets.

Over 10 years more than 15,040,000.00 United States Dollars have been invested in the program. More than 3.4 thousand people were sent for training and internship in priority areas for the national economy. More than 700 of them are in the leading educational and scientific centers of the world located in the USA, Canada, Australia, Great Britain, Ireland, Germany, France, Switzerland, Sweden, Italy, China and other countries. Their success in studies forms a positive image of the Republic of Tatarstan in the country and abroad (Kalantary, 2009).

We place the programs that are implemented between Russian and foreign

universities on the basis of mutual agreements into a separate group - this is the third, *institutional* level of the organization of forms of mobility, initiated directly by the universities themselves.

Interuniversity cooperation, implying academic mobility of students, has many different forms. According to Sadovnichy, students participating in academic mobility are sent to various universities for: training in joint programs (double diploma programs); inclusive training (academic exchange); traineeship; internship (educational and research); participation in seasonal schools. Volodina (2014) in the article “Systematization of forms of international academic mobility of students” presents various forms of international academic mobility depending on their purpose and classifies them in three groups.

Table1.Forms of international academic mobility

Socio-cultural	Educational	Scientific
International exhibition activity	Joint programs of double diploma	Joint scientific research and developments
Summer schools	Inclusive education	Scientific practice and traineeship
Cultural exchange programs	Practice and traineeship	Seminars and conferences
	Summer and language schools	Science and technology exhibition activity
		International competitions for students and Olympiads

Source: Authors (2018)

We have studied the experience of leading Russian universities in organizing academic mobility of students. The National Research University “Higher School of Economics” (HSE) has been successfully implementing the following forms of academic mobility for a long time:

Long-term exchange programs

Traineeships

Summer/winter schools

Double diplomas

The number of foreign participants in incoming academic mobility came to 658 people in the 2016/2017 academic year, while the number of students of the Higher School of Economics (HSE) analyzing abroad under academic mobility programs was 668.

A variety of reasons explain the popularity of the Higher School of Economics among the foreign students:

- University reputation (55%), academic reputation of the curriculum (45%) and courses provided by the university (40%) - long-term training programs (degree mobility);
- The desire to learn more about Russian culture (68%), to learn Russian (59%) and to get to know Moscow better (57%) (Credit mobility).

18% of students of HSE participated in international mobility programs, including 8% - in the language school, 7% - in the summer / winter school, 2% - in the semester program at the foreign university, 1% - in the double diploma programs.

343 students of HSE applied to 61 foreign partner universities for the fall semester of 2017. The most popular universities were the University of Oslo (Norway), the University of Bologna (Italy) and the University of Nijmegen (the Netherlands) (Typical higher school, 2016).

Summer / winter schools covering no more than 3 months are the most popular form of mobility in the Higher School of Economics, despite the fact that the participants pay for their travel, food, accommodation and registration fee. At the same time, some schools are ready to offer a discount for the Higher School of Economics students.

Long-term exchange programs provide for full-time education of a student in a foreign university from 3 to 10 months with obtaining of credits and their addition to a certificate. These programs are implemented within the framework of university or faculty agreements and are free for students of HSE. Participants are responsible for their travel, food, accommodation, insurance and organizational fees.

A double diploma in the Higher School of Economics is an opportunity to analyze under a program developed jointly with a foreign university, with the subsequent obtaining a master's degree. The largest number of double diploma programs is implemented in the field of "Economics" (11 programs) and "Management" (9 programs), most of them are taught in English (Official website of Higher School of Economics, 2017).

Peoples' Friendship University of Russia as one of the leading Russian international universities intensively develops international contacts with a view of enhancing its status in the system of higher education of Russian Federation and further integration into the world educational community. RUDN University cooperates with the countries of Asia, Africa and Latin America, Europe and the

USA. The Commonwealth of Independent States' (CIS) countries such as Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova and Ukraine are priority areas. The University is a member of the International Association of Universities, participates in projects of the UN, UNESCO, the Council of Europe, and is the main university of the CIS network university, coordinator of the SCO network university and participates in the development of the BRICS network university.

The program of double diplomas in Peoples' Friendship University of Russia involves a network educational program, which is implemented together with other (including foreign) educational organizations and suggests the issuance of two or more diplomas by two or more partner organizations. The first half of the training is held on the basis of the Peoples' Friendship University of Russia, the second one - on the basis of a partner university. 63 bilateral programs operate in the University today, most of which are with European universities, universities in China and the CIS (Official website of Peoples' Friendship University, 2017).

Kazan (Volga region) Federal University is engaged in the process of globalization of education and science of the Russian Federation. By the 1st of December 2016, Kazan University formed collaborative partnerships with 300 universities and various organizations from 64 countries, most of which are situated in the European and Asian regions. Every year the number of foreign students in Kazan Federal University is steadily growing: in 2015/2016 it was 3,187 students, in 2016/2017 - 4,252 (Facts on international activities, 2016).

«Regulation on academic mobility of students, post-graduate students, teachers and researchers of Kazan Federal University» is a local normative document regulating the forms and conditions for the implementation of various academic mobility programs for students, post-graduate students, teachers and researchers of the university. Thus, forms of academic mobility for students of the university are:

- inclusive training on student exchange programs in a partner university;
- training in joint educational programs implemented by Kazan Federal University and the partner institution;
- language and scientific traineeships;
- educational internship;
- summer schools;
- participation in conferences, seminars, etc.

In 2016 326 students of Kazan University participated in the mobility programs, most of them (149) studied at least 1 semester in the inclusive training program, 96 students in grant programs, and 81 students in short-term mobility programs. In this case, a student exchange program or a program of two diplomas at the bachelor or master's level is implied under the inclusive training (Facts on international activities, 2016).

SUMMARY

Thus, we distinguish three basic levels of organization of forms of academic mobility of students - international, regional and institutional. The most outstanding project of the international level is the Erasmus program. At the regional level, we presented the Program of outgoing international academic mobility of the International department of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, the Mikhail Prokhorov Fund, the State Program "Global Education" and the "Algarysh" program of the Government of the Republic of Tatarstan. With the wide variety of forms of academic mobility of students, we found that they are most diverse at the institutional level, which is evidence of the actively developing and constantly changing relationships between higher education institutions of different countries. Therefore, we might predict that the presented forms of student mobility will increase in number.

CONCLUSIONS

The current research examined the forms of academic mobility. In this regard, educational and academic centers were studied in the three fields of institutional, regional and international. The theoretical basis of this research was that preference of international education, using international teachers and acceptance of international students could create dynamism in academic environments. Results of the research showed that those educational and scientific centers that used and followed the international educational system had a higher level of vitality and dynamism, the typical example of which was the Kazan Federal University.

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REFERENCES

- A Statistical Overview of the Erasmus Program in 2012-13.** (2015). Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. p. 248.
- Action Plan for International Cooperation** (2014). Published by the NTNU Communication Division, August 2014.

Caulfield, N., Chang, D., Dollard, M. F., Elshaug, C. A. (2004). **Review of Occupational Stress Interventions in Australia**. International Journal of Stress Management, 11, pp.149-166.

Facts on international activities (2016). International Education and Student Mobility Division, KYOTO UNIVERSITY Facts and Figures.

Global Education (2017).**Program of the Russian Federation Government**, URL: www.educationglobal.ru/ns/participant/

Kalantary, K. (2009).**Structural equation modeling in socio – economic research**. Tehran, Saba Farhang, pp. 128-135.

Official website of Higher School of Economics. (2017). URL: www.Analyzeabroad.hse.ru/

Official website of Peoples' Friendship University. (2017).URL: www.rudn.ru/?pagec=5373

Shakirova, A. (2016).**Periods of academic mobility development in Russia**. IEJME: Mathematics Education. Vol. 11. #6. pp. 1643-1649.

Typical higher school. (2016). **Bulletin of the Center for Internal Monitoring**. The National Research University. Higher School of Economics. 2 (24). pp. 1-3.

Volodina, Y. (2014). **Systematization of the students' international mobility forms**. Chelyabinsk State Pedagogics University Journal.#2. pp. 93-102.

Ziyatdinova, J., Bezrukov, A., Sanger, P.A., Osipov, P. (2016). **Best practices of engineering education internationalization in a Russian Top-20 university**. ASEE 2016 International Forum. pp. 1-10.